

Emission of H₂S from livestock farms and methods for its prevention, detection and control

D.S. Tomar¹, Tejeshwari Satpute², Shivam Bharadwaj³ And Parinita Prashar⁴

^{1,2}PhD Scholar, Livestock Production Management Division, ICAR-NDRI, Karnal

³PhD Scholar, Animal Genetics and Breeding Division, ICAR-NDRI, Karnal

⁴Veterinary Officer, Department of Animal Husbandry, H.P.

Introduction

Emissions of potentially harmful gases such as H₂S from confined animal feeding operations have become a major concern in recent years (Aneja *et al.*, 2001). In recent years, the use of liquid manure storage systems has increased significantly. As a quick and affordable way to deal with animal wastes, many dairy and other livestock enterprises as well as certain poultry farms now use liquid manure systems. These systems, particularly if they are incorporated into the barn construction, may pose a serious hazard because of gases produced. Decomposing animal manure gives off a variety of gases including hydrogen sulphide, carbon dioxide and methane. Of all these gases, hydrogen sulphide or more commonly called manure gas, is the most dangerous. Hydrogen Sulphide (H₂S) has been responsible for many animal deaths as well as occasional human deaths. (Farm safety association, 1985)

How Hydrogen Sulphide Is Formed

Decomposition of animal dung results in the formation of hydrogen sulphide. Decomposition of cattle dung produces gases.

- (i) Right after defecation
- (ii) While being stored and treated, and
- (iii) During the application of soil. (Jacobson *et al.*, 2003)

As soon as it is expelled by the animals, the breakdown process starts. Manure is used by microorganisms to produce new cells and to provide energy for synthesis. This process takes place with or without oxygen. However, the type of microbes, and the type of gases that are produced, depend on the environment in which degradation occurs. In anaerobic conditions (without oxygen), typical of most liquid manure systems, hydrogen sulphide will be given off. H₂S is produced as manure decomposes

anaerobically, resulting from the mineralisation of organic sulphur compounds. The amount of H₂S emission depends on the pH, temperature, and liquid phase concentration (USEPA, 2001). Sulfides are present in two forms: neutral and ionic. The neutral H₂S is quickly volatilized, whereas the ionic forms remain dissolved in water. All un-aerated manure storage systems, such as shallow barn gutters, underground storage tanks, or outdoor holding ponds or lagoons, continuously create hydrogen sulphide. Sulphate is responsible for H₂S emission apart from the presence of sulphur containing amino acids (cysteine and methionine) and elements (sulphur) in the diet that directly affect the concentration of H₂S (Zahn *et al.*, 2001). Sulphur compounds released into the atmosphere eventually form sulphate aerosols and acidic compounds (i.e., sulphuric acid or methanesulphonic acid). Sulphate acid deposition can also be detrimental to ecosystems, harming aquatic animals and plants, and damaging a wide range of terrestrial plant life (Aneja *et al.*, 2008).

Properties of Hydrogen Sulphide

Hydrogen sulfide is a colourless, flammable, and very rapidly toxic gas, and is easily soluble in both water and lipids (Xuan *et al.*, 2020). Since hydrogen sulphide is extremely flammable and explosive, it tends to build up in low-lying, poorly ventilated areas. It is also significantly heavier than air. It has a distinct "rotten-egg" odour that can be detected at quite low quantities. The specific gravity of hydrogen sulphide is 1.19, making it about 20% heavier than air.

Hydrogen Sulphide Detection

Odours of hydrogen sulphide can be detected in amounts lower than 1 mg/kg (air). As the gas is concentrated, the smell of hydrogen sulphide will get stronger. At concentrations around 30 ppb the H₂S odour can be detected by over 80% of the population (Schiffman *et al.*, 2002). However, in concentrations of 150 or greater mg/kg (air), a person's ability to detect the gas is affected by temporary paralysis of the olfactory nerves in the nose. Because of this particular characteristic of hydrogen sulphide, it can be exceedingly dangerous to solely rely on odour to alert one to the presence of the gas. The loss of smell in high concentrations could indicate a rise in gas concentrations since the loss of smell occurs instantly in high concentrations. Before entering any place where hydrogen sulphide may be present, the use of hydrogen sulphide monitors, breathing air with a self-contained breathing apparatus, or similar test methods is strongly advised.

Since hydrogen sulphide is a highly hazardous gas, suitable detection systems should be accessible in livestock facilities, particularly during the agitation and pumping of manure. A range of detection tools are available, including Gas Detector Tubes, Continuous Monitors, Personal Monitors, and Portable Monitors. Some of these monitors are easy to use, while others require some calibration and user training. For bigger manure tanks where multiple detectors can be networked to a central control

panel, fixed gas detectors for H₂S are appropriate. Visual and auditory alarms will go out if H₂S exposure exceeds the predetermined exposure level, warning the workers of the threat.

Portable H₂S gas detectors are particularly helpful when working in restricted places and can be used for personal protection as well. Simple to use, with only one button to press, and easily attachable to workers' clothing. When certain levels of gas or gases are discovered, portable gas detectors provide a safe monitoring option by alerting the user. To reduce your risk of inhaling in highly hazardous hydrogen sulphide, use a gas detector tube with an extension hose. For the gas to be measured, the detector tube needs to be particular (hydrogen sulphide). Place the detection tube close to the floor and use the vacuum pump to suck air into the tube while squeezing through a window or other opening.

Evaluation Of Human Health Risks

In high concentrations, hydrogen sulphide, which is categorised as a dangerous gas, will cause virtually immediate poisoning and death. According to the Health & Safety Executive (HSE), 800 ppm is the commonly acknowledged deadly value for 50% of a human population exposed for 5 minutes to hydrogen sulphide gas.

The most common method of exposure for livestock farm workers to hydrogen sulphide is inhalation. Children are especially vulnerable due to their greater lung surface area to body weight ratios. Long-term hydrogen sulphide exposure can be extremely irritating to the skin and eyes. Hydrogen sulfide is also a notable mucous membrane and respiratory tract irritant, and the acute and/or delayed (up to 72 hours after exposure) respiratory distress syndromes are common sequela of prolonged inhalation exposure to non-acutely fatal levels of hydrogen sulfide (Tatum, 1996).

Hydrogen sulfide acts by inactivating mitochondrial cytochrome oxidase, resulting in the failure of oxidative metabolism, histotoxic hypoxia, and acute anion-gap metabolic acidosis. It works in a similar way to cyanide. Due to its acute effects on the brain, acute exposure to high amounts of hydrogen sulphide will cause abrupt collapse and death from central respiratory failure (hydrogen sulphide knock-down effect). Initial CNS stimulation, nausea, headaches, altered gait, dizziness, unsteadiness, tremors, convulsions, skin and eye irritation, coma, respiratory paralysis, and death are signs and symptoms of acute exposure. There are numerous cases of hypoxic brain and heart damage in acute hydrogen sulphide poisoning survivors. Personality changes, memory problems, issues with voluntary muscle movement, and the emergence of involuntary motions can all be signs of hypoxic brain damage (extrapyramidal syndromes).

Hydrogen sulphide causes immediate upper respiratory tract irritation at low concentrations (50 ppm), while long-term exposure can cause pulmonary irritation (cough, shortness of breath, and bronchial or lung hemorrhage, bronchitis, and immediate or delayed pulmonary edema). There could

be a cyanosis. Cardiac arrhythmias are linked to hydrogen sulphide inhalation. Vomiting and nauseousness are also frequent.

Ataxia, conjunctivitis, chronic cough, hypotension, headache, nausea, loss of appetite, weight loss, and cognitive problems are all linked to chronic, recurrent, low-level hydrogen sulphide exposure.

H₂S toxicity has no known effective treatment at this time. The only method of treatment that has been proven to be effective is resuscitation with oxygen. Rescue and treatment of individuals with hydrogen sulfide poisoning is a matter for properly equipped and trained professionals (MSD manual).

Safe Management of a Liquid Manure System (Farm safety association, 1985):

For a liquid manure system to be safely managed in a cattle facility, the ensuing safety measures are imperative:

1. Even when the pit is empty, no one should ever enter a liquid manure pit without wearing a self-contained breathing device. Use a life line that is attached to a person who is not in the danger zone.
2. Avoid letting the manure hole entirely fill up. Air space needed to handle gas concentrations should be 1 to 2 feet.
3. Before beginning the agitation, if at all feasible, reduce the level of liquid manure in the storage facility. As a result, there will be less chance of gas being forced over the floor.
4. Continue to agitate the liquid below the surface. Greater amounts of gas will be emitted if there is significant surface agitation.
5. During pumping and agitation, provide ample ventilation. People should not be let inside the building, and animals should be evacuated if at all feasible.
6. Due to the risks involved in the agitating and pumping processes, two individuals should be present when carrying out these tasks, with one person always being outside of the danger zone.
7. If you have been exposed to hydrogen sulphide at levels high enough to irritate your respiratory tract, speak with your doctor.

Design And Construction of New Facilities (Powers, 2011):

If you're thinking about installing a liquid manure system in a new building, the following things should be taken into account:

1. To avoid the risk of working in a small space, all manure pit pump-out outlets should be situated outside the structure.
2. Storage of liquid manure needs to be kept apart from structures used for livestock. To stop gases

from re-entering the building, connecting drains, gutters, and channels should be equipped with gas traps or some other kind of barrier.

3. To reduce the requirement for agitation, liquid manure collection pits inside of barns should be kept to a minimum volume and divided into tiny compartments.

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